

The *picrate* was prepared in the usual way and was crystallised as red plates from alcohol, m. p. 114°. (Found : N, 9.25. $C_{22}H_{23}O_7N_3$ requires N, 9.50%).

Oxidation of the Ketone (XVI) with Sodium Hypoiodite.—The ketone (XVI : 3.5 g.) was oxidised with sodium hypoiodite solution in the same way as described for the ketone (VII). After working up in the same manner, 1.9 g. of the acid (XII), b.p. 172-75°/6 mm., was obtained. The *S-benzylisothouronium* derivative of the above acid was prepared in the usual way and was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 119° (undepressed on admixture with the sample obtained earlier from the acid, XII).

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FRIEDEL-CRAFTS' REACTION INVOLVING UNSATURATED KETONES AND ESTERS. PART VI. ALKYLATION OF ANISOL WITH ETHYL ALLYLACETATE AND ALLYLACETONE

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Cationoid reaction of ethyl allylacetate and allylacetone with anisol has been studied. Of particular interest is the facile cyclodehydration undergone by the condensation product of anisol with allylacetone. Also, the Friedel-Crafts alkylation products proved to be readily accessible intermediates in convenient syntheses of several methoxynaphthalene homologues.

In earlier communications (Mukherji *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, **17**, 1202; 1953, **18**, 1499; 1954, **19**, 328; this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 697; 1956, **33**, 1), Friedel-Crafts' alkylation of aromatic substrates with ethyl allylacetate and allylacetone was shown to initiate convenient synthetic routes to the different types of polynuclear hydrocarbons. It has now been decided to extend the scope of this method to alkyl aryl ethers. The Friedel-Crafts alkylation of anisol is rather well known (Price, "Organic Reaction", John Wiley, 1949, **3**, 65) and the *para*-orientated products are the preponderant components, although in the case of reaction with *cyclohexene* (Bodroux, *Ann. chim.*, 1929, **x**, 11, 511) the *ortho*-isomer is reported to be in greater proportion.

However, when anisol was subjected to aluminium chloride-catalysed reaction at 0°-5° with ethyl allylacetate, 4-(*p*-anisyl)-valerate (I) was the exclusive product obtained in 31% yield. On hydrolysis (I) gave a quantitative yield of the acid (II). That the product (I) was *para*-orientated was proved by alkaline permanganate oxidation of the

acid (II) to *p*-anisic acid; *o*- or *m*-anisic acid could not be detected. Further, the acid (II) on cyclisation (Johnson and Glenn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1092), reduction (Clemmensen) and dehydrogenation with sulphur gave 1-methyl-6-methoxynaphthalene (V).

To further improve the yield in the Friedel-Crafts alkylation step, attempts were made to perform this reaction under more drastic conditions of temperature, but extensive methylation resulted in intractable material.

Similarly, anisol was condensed with allylacetone when 5-(*p*-anisyl)-hexan-2-one (VI) was obtained in 31% yield. In the reaction with allylacetone the proportion of aluminium chloride used was less as it was observed that with two moles of this reagent the yield of the ketone (VI) decreased, presumably due to concomitant cyclodehydration (*vide infra*). The orientation was established by sodium hypiodite oxidation of the ketonic product (VI) to furnish the acid (II), identified through the mixed melting points of the *S*-benzylisothiuronium derivatives of the two samples of the acid. The ketone (VI) on reduction (sodium and moist ether), followed by cyclisation (sulphuric acid) and dehydrogenation (sulphur), furnished 1:4-dimethyl-6-methoxynaphthalene in a good yield.

In one of our experiments with anisol and allylacetone, the temperature rose as high as 50°, and the product obtained failed to afford the semicarbazone. Examination of this product revealed that the initial Friedel-Crafts alkylation was accompanied *in situ* with cyclodehydration to furnish the dihydro derivative (X), which was confirmed by its dehydrogenation with sulphur to 1:4-dimethyl-6-methoxynaphthalene (VIII). The formation of (X) may be explained on the basis of initial addition of anisyl group to the double bond of allylacetone, followed by cyclodehydration (cf. Grosse *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1938, 3, 137) according to the following scheme :

The above observation on the facile cyclodehydration of (VI) is very interesting in view of the fact that the *meta* positions with respect to the electron donating methoxy group should, on the contrary, exhibit suppressed anionoid activity as evidenced *inter alia* in intramolecular acylation (Johnson, "Organic Reactions", Wiley, 1949, 2, 120).

* EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 4-(p-Anisyl)-valerate (I).—Freshly distilled anisol (75 c.c.) was allowed to react with ethyl allylacetate (14 g.) in presence of AlCl₃ (anhyd., 30 g.) following exactly the procedure recorded by Mukherji *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, 18, 1499), and after working up the reaction mixture in the prescribed way, 8 g. (31%) of ethyl 4-(*p*-anisyl)-valerate, b.p. 152-54°/10 mm., was obtained. (Found: C, 71.34; H, 8.49. C₁₄H₂₀O₃ requires C, 71.16; H, 8.53%).

4-(p-Anisyl)-valeric Acid (II).—Hydrolysis of the above ester (13 g.) was effected by refluxing it with alcoholic KOH (7.5 g. in 5 c.c. water and 165 c.c. alcohol) on the water-bath for 6 hours. On being worked up in the usual way the hydrolysate furnished 10 g. (87%) of 4-(*p*-anisyl)-valeric acid as a colorless oil, b. p. 171-73°/6 mm. (Found: C, 69.0; H, 7.83. C₁₂H₁₈O₃ requires C, 69.21; H, 7.74%).

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Analyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford.

The *S*-benzylisothiouronium derivative was prepared in the usual manner and was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 125-26°. (Found: N, 7.70. $C_{20}H_{26}O_3N_2S$ requires N, 7.48 %).

4-Methyl-7-methoxy-1-tetralone (III).—The acid (II: 10 g.) in dry benzene (20 c.c.) was converted into its acid chloride by PCl_5 (11 g.) in the usual manner and the acid chloride without being isolated was cyclised by aluminium chloride (7.5 g.) according to the conditions described by Mukherji *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) for the preparation of 4:6-dimethyl-1-tetralone, when 4 g. (44%) of the ketone (III), b. p. 102-105°/4 mm., was obtained. (Found: C, 75.62; H, 7.56. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 75.76; H, 7.42%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared by sulphuric acid method and crystallised as orange-red needles from ethyl acetate, m.p. 215-16°. (Found: N, 15.50. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8N_4$ requires N, 15.15%).

1-Methyl-6-methoxytetralin (IV).—The above ketone (III: 3.5 g.) was refluxed with amalgamated zinc (17 g.), toluene (30 c.c.), HCl (conc., 30 c.c.), water (10 c.c.), and glacial acetic acid (1 c.c.) for 36 hours at 120°-130°. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual way when 2.7 g. of the tetralin derivative (IV) was obtained as a colorless oil, b. p. 120-22°/5 mm. (Found: C, 81.53; H, 9.23. $C_{12}H_{16}O$ requires C, 81.77; H, 9.15 %).

1-Methyl-5-methoxynaphthalene (V).—The tetralin (IV: 2.5 g.) was heated with sulphur (1.1 g.) at 180° for about 6 hours and then steam-distilled; the distillate was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer cleared with anhydrous sodium sulphate. Fractionation gave 1.6 g. of the desired product (V), b. p. 135°/10 mm. (Found: C, 83.79; H, 6.93. $C_{12}H_{12}O$ requires C, 83.69; H, 7.02 %).

Oxidation of the Acid (II) with Alkaline Permanganate.—The acid (II: 2.5 g.) was refluxed with a solution of $KMnO_4$ (15 g.) and 2 pellets of NaOH in water (300 c.c.) for 8 hours. The manganese dioxide was removed by filtration. The colorless filtrate was evaporated to a small bulk and then acidified with HCl. *p*-Anisic acid (1.2 g.) was obtained as a crystalline precipitate which was recrystallised from water, m. p. 182-83°. Rosell (*Annalen*, 1869, 151, 30) reported m.p. 184° (decomp.).

5-(*p*-Anisyl)-hexan-2-one (VI).—Anisol (100 c.c.) was condensed with allylacetone (20 g.) in presence of $AlCl_3$ (anhyd., 42 g.) at 0°-5° in the way as for (I), when 13 g. (31%) of 5-(*p*-anisyl)-hexan-2-one was obtained, b.p. 136-40°/7 mm. (Found: C, 75.95; H, 8.53. $C_{13}H_{18}O$ requires C, 75.69; H, 8.80 %).

The semicarbazone was prepared in the usual way and was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 151-52°. (Found: N, 15.72. $C_{14}H_{21}O_3N_2$ requires N, 15.96%).

5-(*p*-Anisyl)-hexan-2-ol (VII).—The above ketone (6 g.) in moist ether (75 c.c.) was treated with sodium (5.5 g.), added gradually in small pieces with stirring. Whenever the reaction had subsided, 1 c.c. of water was added. After the whole of sodium had been added and consumed, the reaction mixture was washed with water and the ethereal layer dried ($CaCl_2$). Fractionation gave the alcohol (VII) (4.2 g., 68%) as a colorless oil, b. p. 135-36°/4 mm. (Found: C, 74.87; H, 9.32. $C_{13}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 74.96; H, 9.68 %).

1:4-Dimethyl-6-methoxytetralin (VIII).—The carbinol (VII : 4 g.) was treated in the cold with ice-cooled H_2SO_4 (d 1.84, 10 c.c.), added dropwise with shaking for 20 minutes. The mixture was then allowed to attain room temperature and worked up in the usual way, when 2.5 g. of the tetralin (VIII) was obtained, b.p. $195-97^\circ/12$ mm. (Found : C, 82.32 ; H, 9.43. $C_{15}H_{18}O$ requires C, 82.06 ; H, 9.54%).

1:4-Dimethyl-6-methoxynaphthalene (IX).—The above tetralin (2 g.) was dehydrogenated with sulphur (0.9 g.) in the same way as described for (V), when 1 g. of (IX), b. p. $156-58^\circ/12$ mm., was obtained. (Found : C, 83.94 ; H, 7.32. $C_{15}H_{14}O$ requires C, 83.83 ; H, 7.58 %).

The picrate was prepared in the usual manner and was crystallised from ethanol, m. p. $107-108^\circ$. (Found : N, 9.70. $C_{19}H_{17}O_8N_3$ requires N, 10.12%).

Oxidation (VI) with Sodium Hypoiodite.—The ketone (VI : 3 g.) in dioxan (60 c.c.) was oxidised in the same way as described in Part V (this issue, p. 1). The oily product was taken up in ether, washed and dried (Na_2SO_4). Fractionation gave 1.65 g. of 4-(*p*-anisyl)-valeric acid, b.p. $178^\circ/7$ mm.

The *S*-benzylisothiuronium derivative, prepared in the prescribed way, was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 119° , undepressed on admixture with the derivative from (II).

1:4-Dimethyl-6-methoxy-1:2-dihydronaphthalene (X).—Anisol (50 c. c.) was condensed with allylacetone (10 g.) in the same way as for (I). But after the addition of aluminium chloride (20.8 g.) the ice-bath was removed and the reaction mixture was allowed to acquire the room temperature (25°) and then warmed on the water-bath at 50° for half an hour and then kept standing overnight. After the usual working up, 10 g. (52%) of (X) was obtained, b.p. $194-98^\circ/mm$. (Found : C, 83.14 ; H, 8.65. $C_{15}H_{16}O$ requires C, 82.91 ; H, 8.57%).

The above dihydronaphthalene (5 g.) was treated with sulphur (1.04 g.) in the same way as for (IV) and the reaction mixture worked up in the usual manner, when 2.5 g. of the desired product, b.p. $156-60^\circ/12$ mm., was obtained. This hydrocarbon was converted into its picrate (5 g.), crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 107° , undepressed when mixed with the picrate of (IX).